

METHODS FOR DEVELOPING PRONUNCIATION IN FRENCH

Narzulloyeva Dilfuza Bahridin qizi

shakhnarzoullayev@gmail.com

Faculty of Foreign Languages of Bukhara State University

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Abstract: One of the languages that people read and speak the most throughout the world is French. Many students find it difficult to pronounce. When compared to other languages, the French language has unique pronunciation traits where the blend of sounds, accent, and intonation are crucial components. This article offers practical techniques, firsthand accounts, and advice on how to master French pronunciation.

Keywords: Romance languages, Latin alphabet, pronunciation of sounds, online resources, apps, pronunciation exercises.

I. INTRODUCTION

The French language, known for its beauty and sophistication, is an interesting and enlightening language for many people. However, French pronunciation can be a challenge for many new learners. Unlike words from Romance languages like Italian and Spanish, which are usually entirely phonetic, French words are difficult to "sound out" correctly and necessitate keeping your mouth shut far more often than open. French seems quite delicate to English speakers; numerous tiny motions at the front of the lips and rear of the throat are needed, which can make us feel a little lost for words. It's common knowledge that you can speak a French word by just omitting the final few letters, but which ones? There are numerous exceptions to the general rule that French words are typically substantially lengthier when written down than when spoken. Fortunately, French phrases will start to flow much more naturally once you learn a few important pronunciation guidelines about how particular letters react to one another. Similar to the English language, the French writing system employs the 26-letter Latin alphabet. Thirty-six distinct sounds are produced from these twenty-six letters (which is somewhat fewer than the forty-four sounds in English). Three of these 26 letters are primarily used as loanwords. These are terms that have been borrowed, without translation, from other languages. K, W, and, to a lesser extent, Y are these letters. Six of the fourteen vowel sounds in the French language are absent from the English language. In addition, twenty-two consonant sounds are present, four of which are absent from English.

French pronunciation

Letter(s)	Pronunciation & example	Letter(s)	Pronunciation & example
a	as a in father - ami	nasal n	no equivalent - pain
ai	as e in bed - lait	o	as o in solo - opéra
au	as o in odd - chaud	oi	as oi in foie gras - trois
b	as b in buy - bonbons	ou	as oo in cool - nous
c	as c in cost - café	p	as p in pie - père
c	as c in cell - cerise	ph	as ph in phone - phare
ç	as ç in façade - ça va	q	as q in pique - banque
ch	as sh in shor - chaud	r	no equivalent - rouge
d	as d in doll - mardi	s	as s in stone - poisson
e, eu	no equivalent - le, feu	s	as z in zap - oiseau
é, è, ê	as e in elephant - tête	sc	as sc in science - scie
eau	as o in old - beau	sc	as sc in scold - escale
f	as f in fat - neuf	t	as t in toe - tarte
g	as g in grape - gare	th	no equivalent - thé
g	as g in mirage - gèle	ti	as si in silly - attention
h	as h in hour - hiver	u, ue	as u in user - tu, saluer
i	as i in naive - dix	ui	no equivalent - nuit
j	as j in déjà vu - jambon	v	as v in vain - vert
k	as k in kit - ski	w	as v in van - wagon
l	as l in like - fleur	x	as x in express - taxe
m	as m in mom - madame	x	as x in exit - exemplaire
nasal m	no equivalent - parfum	y	as y in yes - yeux
n	as n in no - neuf	z	as z in zone - zéro

mondly

(PICTURE 1[1])

II. METHODS

The following methods and tips are recommended for learning pure pronunciation in French. One of the most important aspects of learning French is listening skills.

1. Working with the audience

Various audio materials can be used to improve pronunciation by listening. For example, listening to French movies, music, or podcasts can help students learn the correct pronunciation. Pronunciation of sounds can be mastered well by applying theoretical knowledge in practice.

For example:

- In oral speech, only the participle is pronounced in the combination *Je suis*

- The compound *tu es* is pronounced as t'es (te) in oral speech.

It is better to learn such situations in French by watching or listening and using them in speech and every week, students can watch a French movie or podcast, take notes on the vocabulary, and then speak it out. Speaking and listening abilities are integrated in this process.

2. Pronunciation courses and online resources

These days, learning French pronunciation is made easier with the abundance of online resources available. For instance, a variety of videos on YouTube provide students with the proper pronunciation. Additionally, apps like Babel and Duolingo yield good outcomes. Every day, students should spend 15 to 20 minutes using these applications to learn new words and concentrate on pronouncing them correctly.

3. Using proverbs and poems

Pronunciation exercises with French poems or proverbs can be quite beneficial. This aids with vocabulary growth as well as comprehension of the French language's melody and rhythm.

For example:

Si tu crois tout ce que tu lis, tu ferais mieux de ne pas lire.

Through this proverb, the student will learn the difference between **u** and **ou** sounds and learn to pronounce them correctly. Besides, learning French using proverbs doesn't have to be boring. When learning a language, consistency is important to consider and can lead to positive outcomes.

III. RESULTS

The pronunciation of sounds in French is close to each other, therefore, it is possible to overcome the difficulties encountered by students based on learning through the above methods. If during the lesson students watch short videos and pay attention to the words used in them, through this process they can acquire new words and the pronunciation of these words as well as grammar rules. If everyone uses appropriate methods and methods in the process of language learning, this process will be faster and the desired results can be achieved. For this, it is necessary to constantly practice the language.

IV. DISCUSSION

Acquiring proficiency in French pronunciation necessitates a comprehensive strategy that encompasses both auditory discrimination and physical articulation abilities. Many language learners have found success when using technology, such as applications for language learning, in conjunction with more conventional techniques, such as phonetic training and listening exercises.

Moreover, practice consistently is essential; even little daily sessions might result in significant improvement over time. For best outcomes, educators should advise students to combine these strategies in a way that suits their unique learning preferences.

V. CONCLUSION

To sum up, becoming proficient in pronunciation is crucial to becoming fluent in French. Through a variety of methods, including phonetic training, listening exercises, shadowing techniques, articulation drills, and technology use, students can improve their pronunciation while having fun and mastering a lovely language.

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